

THE ASSOCIATION OF BOWEL DISEASE WITH VITAMIN C DEFICIENCY.

BY

LIEUT.-COL. F. P. MACKIE, O.B.E., V.H.S., I.M.S.,

AND

G. D. CHITRE, L.M. & S., B.M.S.

(Being Part III of the Sprue Investigation at the Haffkine Institute, Parcel,
Bombay.)

[Received for publication, February 27, 1928.]

WE attempted in a series of experiments detailed in a previous paper* to produce the clinical feature of sprue in animals by infecting them with sprue faeces or with monilia isolated therefrom. In some of these experiments we tried to induce susceptibility in monkeys by keeping them on a diet deficient in vitamin C. We were not successful in reproducing sprue in these animals, but we found that avitaminosis in itself produced an increased susceptibility to disease of the intestinal tract.

We used sixteen monkeys (*M. sinicus* and *rhesus*) in two batches. The first batch included ten monkeys including four controls which latter were fed on a normal diet and which did not receive infected material. In this batch the six monkeys fed on a deficient diet which also received infective feeds of sprue material, all developed an inflammatory or degenerative condition of the alimentary tract resembling dysentery, whilst the four control monkeys remained quite free from this disease.

This batch of experiments suggested that the feeds of infective material from sprue cases were responsible for the bowel disease referred to.

The second batch of experiments was more exacting in that all the six monkeys were maintained on a deficient diet, but the three controls received no infective feeds. The six animals were housed on the same verandah but were separate from each other. All six animals developed the same clinical symptoms and showed the same post-mortem conditions, so it is fair to assume that the causative or predisposing factor was the deficiency in vitamin C and not the infected feeds.

* 'Animal Experiments and Sprue' (this number), pp. 49-75.

78 Association of Bowel Disease with Vitamin C Deficiency.

The dietary given to induce scurvy was that recommended by Lieutenant-Colonel R. McCarrison, I.M.S., and consisted of—

Polished rice (boiled)	..	..	..	100 grms.
Ground-nuts (parched)	..	..	..	30 grms.
Autoclaved milk	..	..	..	200 c.cs.
Butter	..	..	..	10 grms.
Orange juice	..	..	..	2 c.cs.

The infective feeds of sprue material were generally given when the animals began to lose weight and to exhibit symptoms of ill health. Where the scorbutic condition was advancing too rapidly, an attempt was made to check it by giving a small amount of orange juice or, in one or two cases, by putting the animal back on a full normal diet. In two animals so treated the signs of dysentery receded and the animals quickly recovered (Monkeys 279 and 280), but in monkeys in which a more marked scorbutic condition was present the exhibition of vitamin C was too late to save them.

The most marked result was a loss of weight. This was generally slight at first and was represented by a slow but steady decline in the earlier weeks. When once the decline was established, there came a point when the weight came tumbling down especially with the onset of dysentery and the loss increased in rapidity till the animal died. In some animals no definite signs of scurvy appeared or were found after death, but in others definite scorbutic signs appeared, such as puffiness and ecchymosis around the eyelids or other parts of the face. Small hæmorrhages or bruises under the skin and sometimes hæmorrhages into the muscles were found post-mortem. Loosening of the teeth and bleeding from the gums were seen in the more severe cases. Apathy, wasting and 'staring' of the coat were common signs, but diarrhoea was not a prominent feature during life except in a few cases.

The infected feeds were generally commenced when the animals' weight began to decline and consisted of saline suspensions of the fresh fæces of human sprue cases or of cultures of *Monilia psilosis* isolated therefrom or of both together.

Post-mortem appearances.

On opening the abdomen, the intestine was generally seen to be injected and the large bowel was often thickened and congested. No obvious naked eye changes were seen in the viscera, but the heart was generally pale and flabby.

On opening up the alimentary canal, small hæmorrhages or diffuse ecchymosis were sometimes present in the stomach. The small intestines were frequently congested, but rarely showed much change till the lower part of the ileum was reached.

At this level the mucous membrane was thickened and velvety, whilst small superficial erosions were occasionally present, but ulceration was never seen above the level of the ileocæcal valve.

The large intestine showed well-marked changes in every case, particularly in the cæcum and the descending colon and sigmoid. The changes varied from

deep congestion with thickening of the mucous and submucous layers to frank ulceration and widespread superficial sloughing of the mucous membrane. Perforation of the cæcum and invasion of the adjoining surface of the liver was noted in one case. The condition in the severe cases resembled a toxic form of dysentery with ulcers, hæmorrhages and surface sloughs. The impression one gained was that the inflammatory changes were less obvious than those of degeneration and this was borne out by a study of the micro-histology.

Micro-histology.

The stomach and upper part of the small intestine rarely showed any change except for small hæmorrhages which were part of the scorbutic state. The lower portion of the ileum was generally congested and the mucous membrane thickened. In places there was loss of staining power and cloudy swelling of the superficial layers suggesting an early stage of toxæmia. The large intestine in every instance showed these inflammatory and toxic changes more profoundly. Wide areas were almost denuded of the surface epithelium which lay in the lumen in a state of coagulative necrosis containing swarms of bacteria. Ulceration was seen in some specimens extending to the submucosa or more rarely to the muscular coat. In the more profound cases the whole of the gut wall was swollen and the muscle cells showed diffuse eosin staining with loss of nuclear definition as if the local toxins had affected these structures also.

The parenchyma of the liver, kidney and mesenteric glands often showed well-marked toxic changes as evidenced by obliteration of cell outlines, diffuse staining and small celled infiltration.

The blood of some of the animals was studied during life and revealed a progressive anæmia without signs of regeneration and with little change in the bone marrow after death. The intestinal mucosa was invaded by numerous bacteria chiefly cocci and Gram-negative coliforms which were mostly in the degenerated layers or in sloughs, but there was some evidence of deeper invasion of bacteria into the living tissues. Monilia were never seen to have invaded the living tissues, though they were often present in the fæcal contents and in the sloughs.

Bacteriological examination of the diseased intestine.

Examinations of the dysentery-like fæces both before life and immediately after death were carried out in nearly every case. Fresh scrapings from the large intestine never showed amœbæ or their cysts. Flagellates and blastocysts and bodies resembling coccidia were found on occasions. Large undulating slowly-motile bacteria were seen on several occasions but were not grown in any of the media used.

The fæcal organisms were studied in most cases, but only on one occasion was a dysentery-like organism (of Flexner Y type) isolated and a proteus-like bacillus also in one or two occasions. Non-hæmolytic cocci were numerous in all cases. Monilia of *psilosis* type were sometimes isolated from the fæces before the experiment was begun and in most cases were recovered from the diarrhoeal or dysenteric stools, but there is no reason to associate them with the evolution of the bowel

disease. (Fuller details will be found in the report on each monkey in the attached protocols.)

REMARKS.

On going through such literature as we have at our disposal, we find that though a great deal of work has been done on experimental scurvy in animals (including monkeys), references to lesions of the intestinal tract are very infrequent and it is clear that the extensive dysentery-like condition present in our monkeys is somewhat exceptional.

Thus Harden and Silva (1918-1919) describe in detail the symptomatology of experimental scurvy in monkeys but make no reference to any intestinal lesions.

On the subject of vitamins and infection, Findlay (1922) had made a series of observations on guinea-pigs suffering from experimental scurvy. No mention is made of the condition of the alimentary tract. He confirms the question of lowered resistance to bacterial infection. The result of his experiment with four species of bacteria shows that guinea-pigs, fed on a diet deficient in vitamin C, succumb to a smaller infecting dose of bacteria than animals fed on a complete diet and that the symptoms of toxæmia are manifested more rapidly in scorbutic than in control pigs. He associates this fact with an altered condition of the bone marrow and concludes that guinea-pigs with chronic scurvy, though showing few clinical symptoms, are less resistant to bacterial infection.

Several writers, Cohen and Mendel (1918), Jackson and Moody (1916), point out the lowered resistance to bacterial invasion which is seen in scorbutic animals, and this suggests that the dysentery-like condition found in our animals may have been due to the invasion of faecal organisms of exalted virulence rather than to specific organisms of human dysentery. The occasional absence of all clinical signs of dysentery during life in spite of the ulcerated condition present in the large intestine as revealed by necropsy is a remarkable clinical fact.

It recalls an incident which the senior writer witnessed in Mesopotamia during the late war. An officer had been invalided from the front after suffering considerable hardship, including poor feeding, and was admitted to the officers' hospital in Baghdad for some minor surgical condition. He was under the close observation of experienced surgeons and trained nurses for a week after admission but at no time presented any signs of intestinal disease and his motions were reported to be normal. He died suddenly of heart failure (in itself a suspicious sign of avitaminosis) and at the autopsy his large intestine was found to be in a condition resembling acute dysentery with extensive superficial ulceration and sloughing of the mucous membrane. Scurvy was at that time rife in the outposts of the war area and one is tempted to compare the condition in this patient with what one observed in several of the monkeys in the present experiments. About the same time a terrific outbreak of dysentery occurred amongst a number of refugees who had recently arrived in Baghdad in a condition of extreme malnutrition and poverty, being a survival of those who escaped massacre at the hands of the Turks in the highlands of Persia. The appalling severity of the epidemic (resembling cholera at its worst) and the profound intestinal changes

found at the post-mortem impressed one with the conviction that the condition of malnutrition was largely responsible for the virulence of the epidemic. The prevailing organism found was Shiga's bacillus, but the predisposing cause was the scorbutic or sub-scorbutic state which starvation had impressed on these unfortunate people.

The writer who has laid most stress on the intestinal changes in avitaminosis is McCarrison (1918) and he also has called attention to the deficient resistance to bacterial invasion which is brought about by a vitamin-deficient diet. His principal researches in this connection are described in two papers (McCarrison, 1919 and 1920) and an abstract of these papers is given in *Brit. Med. Jour.*, February 21, 1920, p. 249. A study of these researches reveals results with which the observations in the present paper are in close accord.

The symptoms and progress of the disease in monkeys as also the post-mortem signs and the morbid histology are almost precisely those which we have described, the only difference being that in McCarrison's series the duodenum and upper part of the small intestine were equally affected with the large intestine, whereas in our series the upper part of the alimentary canal was almost always free from disease. McCarrison appears to have satisfied himself of the existence of amœbic infection in some of his cases, whereas we were unable to find any such cause. He did not carry out bacteriological examinations of the intestinal contents so that the causation of the dysentery-like condition, if bacterial, was not demonstrated in his animals.

CONCLUSIONS.

1. Monkeys which are fed on a dietary deficient in or lacking 'vitamin C' become debilitated and anæmic, lose weight rapidly and generally suffer from a terminal dysentery which ends in death. Definite signs of scurvy appear in most of the animals.

2. This scorbutic condition can be checked by the administration of orange juice or by a return to a normal dietary provided it is not advanced. When once the scorbutic condition is well established, this treatment cannot be depended upon to save the animals' lives.

3. The post-mortem signs are most marked in the large intestine which shows a succession of changes suggestive of local poisoning. These signs vary from local congestion and thickening of the mucous membrane to a condition indistinguishable from ulcerating and sloughing dysentery.

4. The morbid histology suggests degenerative changes due to the action of a toxin to which inflammatory changes are added secondarily.

5. Specific excitants of dysentery such as amœbæ or dysentery bacilli are not found in the large majority of cases.

6. The commoner fæcal flora are found in some cases to have invaded the living tissues of the bowel wall and this suggests that the toxic changes observed are the effect of such bacteria acting on tissues devitalised by the ill-balanced dietary.

7. These changes appeared in the alimentary canal in all animals kept on a diet deficient in vitamin C whether given infective spruce material or not.

82 *Association of Bowel Disease with Vitamin C Deficiency.*

Monilia were not found to have invaded the diseased areas nor can the changes be attributed to their action.

8. A defective dietary by itself acts as a powerful predisposing cause of bowel derangements and acts probably by reducing the natural resistance of the intestinal epithelium to the invasion of bacteria or their toxins.

REFERENCES.

- COHEN and MENDEL (1918) .. Experimental Scurvy in Guinea-pigs in Relation to the Diet. *Jour. Biol. Chem.*, Vol. XXXV, p. 425.
- HARDEN and SILVA (1918-1919) .. Experimental Scurvy in Monkeys. *Jour. Path. and Bact.*, No. 3, p. 246.
- FINDLAY (1923) .. *Jour. Path. and Bact.*, Vol. XXVI, No. 1.
- JACKSON and MOODY (1916) .. Bacteriological Studies on Experimental Scurvy in Guinea-pigs. *Jour. Inf. Dis.*, Vol. XIX, Sept., p. 511.
- McCARRISON (1918) .. The Pathogenesis of Deficiency Disease. *Ind. Jour. Med. Res.*, Vol. VI, Jan., p. 344.
- McCARRISON (1919) .. The Pathogenesis of Deficiency Disease: (1) The Effect of Autocalved Rice Diets on the Gastro-intestinal Tract of Monkeys. *Ind. Jour. Med. Res.*, Vol. VII, No. 2, Oct., p. 283; (2) The General Effects of Deficient Diets on Monkeys. *Ibid.*, Vol. VIII, p. 308.

PROTOCOLS.

Protocol I.

Monkey 278.

Put on deficiency diet on 25th February 1927.

Infected feeds, 29th March 1927, saline suspension of sprue fæces.

2nd April 1927, culture from sprue fæces.

8th April 1927, saline suspension of sprue fæces.

19th May 1927 " " " "

11th June 1927 " " " "

Clinical Course.—Gradual loss of weight from 1,600 to 1,300 grammes (*vide* Charts I and II). No subcutaneous hæmorrhages or bleeding of gums noted. Signs of dysentery set in on 20th June 1927. Fæces were normal till this date, but subsequently they became loose and contained blood and mucus. Blood films examined during the course of the experiment showed no abnormality. Monilia of 'M' type were found on two occasions in the fæces before the experiment was begun. *M. psilosis* found on several occasions after commencement of infected feeds and also after death.

Bacteriology of fæces after the onset of dysentery—

(1) Numerous strains of a Gram-positive coccus giving the following reactions—acid in lactose, glucose, maltose, saccharose, galactose and milk. Mannite and dulcitol nil.

(2) None of these strains were hæmolytic.

(3) Strains giving the reaction of *B. coli* or *B. anserogenes*.

(4) Strains giving the reactions resembling *B. paracolon*.

(5) A strain resembling *B. faecalis alcaligenes*.

Post-mortem Signs.—Died 22nd June 1927.

Stomach deeply injected and shows submucous hæmorrhages. Small intestine deeply injected, mucous membrane velvety, no surface lesions.

Large intestine acutely inflamed and shows the presence of small superficial ulcers and erosions.

No naked eye changes in the other organs.

Femur contains red marrow.

No monilia found in heart's blood or viscera.

Fresh scrapings from the inflamed gut showed trichomonads, yeasts and blastocysts but no amœbæ or cysts.

Micro-histology.—Stomach normal.

Small intestine showed some aggregation of small cells under mucosa and epithelium was in a condition of cloudy swelling. Large intestine showed early coagulative necrosis of superficial layers of epithelium with denudation and actual ulceration extending to submucous layer in places. The muscular coat was swollen and blurred as if toxic. Crowds of bacilli in necrosed areas. Signs mostly toxic and little evidence of inflammation.

Kidney epithelium showed toxic changes.

Monkey 279.

Put on deficiency diet on 25th February 1927.

Infected material given:—

29th March 1927, saline suspension of sprue fæces.

2nd April 1927, culture from sprue fæces.

8th April 1927, saline suspension of sprue fæces.

19th May 1927 " " " "

11th June 1927 " " " "

Clinical Course.—Weight fell gradually from 2,000 to 1,850 grammes between commencement of experiment to middle of May. Thence dropped rapidly to 1,400 grammes about 20th June. Then began to rise and reached 1,850 in mid-September. Showed signs of dysentery on 21st June 1927. Continued ill for ten days showing blood-stained mucus and made gradual recovery after having been put back on full diet on 26th June 1927. Blood examinations at the height of dysentery showed severe anæmia:

R.B.C.	..	..	..	1,375,000
W.B.C.	..	..	..	12,500
Hb.	..	..	..	50 per cent.
H.I.	..	..	..	1·8

No nucleated reds.

Bacteriology of Fæces.—Fresh preparations showed trichomonads and their cysts, yeasts and their mycelia, a few bodies resembling coccidia. No amoebæ. Bacterial flora appeared normal.

Previous to commencement of experiment, monilia of *psilosis* type and of M type (cryptococcus) were found and subsequent to giving infected material *M. psilosis* and cryptococci were again found.

Bacteriology of fæces was not done.

Result.—The animal developed dysentery but recovered on being placed on a diet abundant in vitamin C.

Monkey 280.

Deficiency diet begun on 25th February 1927.

Fæcal examination previous to giving infected material; monilia of species undetermined found on one occasion.

Infected feeds:—

29th March 1927, saline suspension sprue fæces.

2nd April 1927, culture from sprue fæces.

8th April 1927, saline suspension sprue fæces.

19th May 1927 " " " "

11th June 1927 " " " "

Clinical Course.—Showed gradual decline in weight from 1,630 to 1,480 grammes and a sudden drop about the middle of May to 1,240 grammes. At the end of May, began to rise in weight and eventually approached 1,600 grammes.

Diarrhoea commenced on 26th May 1927, which continued off and on till the end of June. The fæces at their worst were thin and sanious-like meat juice. The monkey was put on ordinary diet on 26th May 1927, when the dysentery symptoms started; but the symptoms continued off and on for a month and then gradually cleared up as the animal improved in weight and in general health.

Examination of Stool.—On 20th June 1927. Some flagellates, trichomonas and cysts. Yeasts. Bodies resembling coccidia. No amœbæ seen. Blastocysts present. The fæces were not examined bacteriologically. Monilia of types *M. psilosis*, *krusei* and 'M' cryptococcus were isolated from stools during the course of the dysentery.

Remarks.—This animal began to show signs of dysentery and marked loss of weight two months after the first infected feed. It was then put back on full diet and the dysenteric signs gradually subsided and a month later the animal began to resume its normal health.

Monkey 281.

Put on deficiency diet on 25th February 1927.

Fæcal examination previous to infected feeds. *M. psilosis* and cryptococcus (M type) present.

Infected feeds:—

29th March 1927, saline suspension sprue fæces.

2nd April 1927, culture from sprue fæces.

8th April 1927, saline suspension sprue fæces.

19th May 1927 " " " "

11th June 1927 " " " "

Clinical Course.—The animal began to lose weight soon after the dietary was curtailed and dropped from 1,750 to 1,600 grammes by mid-May. After this dropped rapidly till date of its death on June 23rd, when it weighed 1,000 grammes.

Developed dysentery on 20th June 1927. Motions resembled liquid meat juice with blood-tinged mucus and the animal was very anæmic and the blood films showed anisocytosis, and poikilocytosis without nucleated red cells or other signs of regeneration.

Examination of Stool.—20th June 1927. Flagellates and cysts with yeasts and mycelia, a few coccidia-like bodies. No amœbæ seen. Monilia of *psilosis*, *krusei* and *cryptococcus* types were isolated from the fæces. Gram-positive cocci giving reactions similar to those described under Monkey 278 were numerous. Those of the coli group were abundant. Several strains of a Gram-negative, non-motile aerobic bacillus of coliform type having the following sugar reactions—lactose and dulcitate negative, acid only in glucose, saccharose, mannite and milk. (The reactions in maltose and galactose were inconclusive.) These strains were not agglutinated by any of the high titre dysentery sera.

Post-mortem Appearances.—Died on 24th June 1927. There were abundant submucous hæmorrhages near the pyloric end of the stomach. The small intestine was injected but showed no breach of surface. The large intestine was

inflamed throughout and covered with mucus. No ulcers were seen, but the gut was thickened and the submucous and mucous coats were in a state of subacute inflammation.

Micro-histology.—The glands at pyloric end of the stomach were markedly degenerated almost resembling amyloid substance but there were no signs of inflammation. The cæcum showed extensive degeneration of surface epithelium without inflammatory reaction. The prevailing organisms were large curved beaded Gram-positive bacteria resembling those showing serpiginous motions seen in fresh preparation. The signs in the large intestine were less marked but there was some superficial necrosis of mucous membrane. Liver, kidney and spleen showed no obvious changes.

Monkey 282.

Deficiency diet begun on 25th February 1927.

Fæcal examinations showed no monilia.

Infected feeds:—

25th April 1927, culture of *M. psilosis* (Ashford) (previously passed through guinea-pig).

21st May 1927, culture of another strain of *M. psilosis* also from sprue case.

Clinical Course.—Began to lose weight soon after the first infected feed and dropped rapidly from 1,600 to 1,040 grammes during a period of seven weeks, after which it was killed on account of its advanced condition of debility. Developed diarrhœa on 19th May 1927. Motions became dysenteric on 11th June 1927, consisting of blood-tinged mucus, with loose green and blood-stained fæces. Monkey put on ordinary diet on 13th June 1927 continued to lose weight and the dysentery continued. The blood was examined on three occasions after the onset of diarrhœa, but did not show any abnormal cytology.

Fæcal Examination.—13th June 1927. Flagellates present and a number of large slowly undulating bacilli with sinuous outline. *M. psilosis* and *M. krusei* were recovered from the fæces. Bacteriological examination showed only cocci and coliform bacilli. No lactose non-fermenters were found and the large bacilli above referred to were not found on the (aerobic) plates.

Post-mortem.—Killed on 15th June 1927 in a very emaciated condition (weight 1,040 grammes). The large intestine was distended and thickened, the mucous membrane was velvety and much thickened as was also the submucous layer. Some hæmorrhagic areas were noted but no actual ulceration. The small intestine presented no naked eye changes. There was some blood-stained fluid in the peritoneal cavity but no pus or adhesions. The bone marrow appeared normal.

Micro-histology.—The stomach and duodenum were normal. The cæcum and ascending colon showed denudation of epithelium in some areas and superficial erosion not amounting to actual ulceration. Some superficial small celled and lymphoid exudation in submucosa but very little sign of inflammation or congestion, but more those of toxic or degenerative changes.

Monkey 283.

Deficiency diet begun on 25th February 1927.

Faecal examinations showed monilia of 'M' type (cryptococcus).

Infected feeds:—

25th April 1927, culture of *M. psilosis* from sprue patient (previously passed through guinea-pig).

21st May 1927, another strain of some monilia from sprue faeces.

Clinical Course.—The weight fell gradually from 1,640 grammes to 1,050 grammes at the autopsy. Dysentery commenced on 11th June 1927. Blood-tinged mucus with liquid or semi-solid greenish or blood-streaked faeces. The cytology of the blood remained normal. Put on ordinary diet on 13th June 1927, but did not recover and died on 17th June 1927.

Faecal Examination.—Fresh preparation showed nothing abnormal. Bacteriological examination showed the usual flora, and no organisms of dysentery group or other lactose non-fermenters were found. *M. psilosis* was recovered from the faeces.

Post-mortem on 17th June 1927.—The large intestine was in a condition of subacute dysentery with erosion of surface and small ulcers and a thick layer of blood-stained mucus. The small intestine was infected but showed no ulceration. The other organs including the bone marrow were normal.

Micro-histology.—The whole of the large bowel from the caecum to the rectum showed varying degrees of coagulation necrosis of whole depth of epithelium which in most areas had separated off or lay attached. The necrotic tissues swarmed with bacteria which penetrated to the submucous coat. Very little inflammatory reaction considering the profound changes seen in the mucous membrane. The mesenteric glands draining the affected area were intensely congested and hyperplastic and many large macrophages were present amongst the lymphoid tissue.

Monkeys 284, 285, 286 and 287.

These were control monkeys fed on ordinary diet to whom no infected feeds were given. The first two kept their weight, remained healthy and were returned to stock. The other two died seven to ten months after commencement of observation of causes unknown (one probably caused by injury during handling). No signs of dysentery were found in either case.

Monkey 327.

Deficiency diet begun on 8th August 1927.

Infected feeds:—

23rd August 1927, culture of *M. psilosis* (Gomez).

29th August 1927 " " "

30th August 1927 " " " (after passage through animals).

6th September 1927 " " "

1st September 1927 " " "

17th October 1927, saline suspension of sprue faeces.

Clinical Course.—The maximum weight of the animal, 3,370 grammes, was noted at the beginning of October, after which it fell almost vertically till 26th November 1927, when it weighed 2,190 grammes and was killed in a state of extreme emaciation. Commenced to show signs of scurvy on 8th October 1927, eyelids swollen and ecchymosis of the face, gums scorbutic and bleeding, conjunctiva inflamed, later some teeth fell out and signs of scurvy increased. No signs of dysentery or diarrhoea during life.

Bacteriological Examination.—The faeces contained a coliform Gram-negative bacillus, forming acid in lactose and acid and gas in glucose, maltose, saccharose and mannite, presumably one of the *B. coli* group. Numerous Gram-positive cocci giving acid in glucose, lactose, maltose, saccharose and mannite, acid and clot in milk. No lactose non-fermenters were found. *M. psilosis* and streptococci recovered from the intestinal contents.

Post-mortem.—The large intestine and especially the caecum was inflamed and the mucous membrane thickened and velvety. The walls were injected and thickened but no ulceration was seen. The condition of the ileum was similar, but in the small bowel there was only thickening of the mucous membrane without denudation. The other organs showed no change.

Micro-histology.—The alimentary canal down to the lower end of the ileum showed little alteration, but at that level there was desquamation of surface epithelium and coagulation necrosis of these structures. The large intestine was more extensively diseased and the mucosa was affected as far down as the sub-mucous and muscular layer. There was loss of staining reaction, a condition of lymphoid hyperplasia and well-marked congestion. Blood was extravasated widely into the mucous and submucous layers and the muscular layers were in a state of cloudy swelling or early toxic necrosis. The liver and kidney showed marked toxic changes. The liver showed abundance of hæmosiderin.

Monkey 328.

Deficiency diet begun on 8th August 1927.

Infected feeds:—

12th September 1927, saline suspension of sprue faeces (Gomez).
17th October 1927

Clinical Course.—The animal kept its weight fairly well, 3,600 to 3,400 grammes, for about three months and then rapidly dropped to about 3,200 grammes in the last two weeks of life. General condition was fairly good till just before death and the animal showed no evidence of scurvy and no signs of diarrhoea or dysentery during life. It died unexpectedly on 21st November 1927.

Bacteriological Examination.—No amœbæ or other protozoa seen. The large undulating motile bacillus previously noted was abundant. The usual cocci and coliform bacilli were found on culture and otherwise the predominant bacillus was a thin bacillus, Gram-negative and non-motile, which fermented glucose, maltose and saccharose, acid without clot in milk, and produced indole. It did not ferment lactose, mannite or dulcitol. It was isolated.

Post-mortem.—The stomach, duodenum and upper part of small intestine were normal, but the lower part of the ileum was thickened and injected and the mucous membrane was soft and velvety and showed small hæmorrhages but no breach of surface to the naked eye. The cæcum and the rest of the large intestine were in a state of subacute dysentery. The mucous membrane was swollen and inflamed and standing out on its surface were marked conical and nipple-shaped elevations almost suggesting new growth. These elevations were capped with an ulcer or grænish slough. The rectum showed more general thickening of mucous and submucous coats without visible ulceration. This condition of the large intestine is represented in Plate I.

Micro-histology.—The intestinal changes in this animal were more widespread as the small intestine shows degeneration and desquamation of superficial layers of mucosa with lymphoid hyperplasia and inflammatory reaction of the submucosa. The muscular layers stained diffusely with eosin and the nuclei were blurred and indistinct. The changes in the large bowel were still more extensive, the mucosa having sloughed in several places and the submucosa was infiltrated with macrophages and inflammatory cells. The muscle layers showed toxic degeneration, and masses of bacteria, mostly cocci, were lying in the mucosa and submucosa. The liver and kidneys showed advanced toxic poisoning and the spleen cells to a less extent. There was no excess of hæmosiderin in the liver.

Monkey 329.

Deficiency diet begun on 8th August 1927.

Infected feeds:—

12th September 1927, saline suspension of sprue fæces (Gomez).

17th September 1927 " " " "

Clinical Course.—Original weight of the animal was 2,910 grammes and fluctuated till the middle of October, after which it fell almost vertically till its death on 21st November 1927, when its weight was 1,560 grammes. It commenced to show signs of scurvy on 30th September 1927, swelling and ecchymosis of eyelids, and scorbutic gums. No signs of diarrhœa or dysentery were present up to the time of its death.

Bacteriological Examination.—The animal died during the night and showed signs of decomposition. No cultures were made.

Post-mortem.—The upper part of the gut was apparently normal, but the whole of the large intestine was in a state of subacute dysentery with much thickening of mucous and submucous coats and a few small ulcers and punctate hæmorrhages and thick tenacious mucus. Decomposition was evident so the organs were not kept for section.

CONTROL, MONKEYS 330, 331 AND 332.

Kept on deficiency diet but given no infected feeds.

Control Monkey 330.

Deficiency diet begun on 8th August 1927.

Clinical Course.—Maximum weight 2,950 grammes noted about two months after commencement of experiment. Fell gradually till mid-November, when it was recorded as 2,870 grammes. After this the weight dropped rapidly and was 2,150 grammes at death. *Showed some loosening of teeth about 14th October 1927, but no other signs of scurvy and it remained active till 30th November 1927, when it suddenly fell ill, developed dysentery and died on 1st December 1927.

Bacteriological Examination.—The dysenteric fæces, both before and after death, were examined but showed no amœbæ or cysts. Some flagellates and spirochætes were present. On culture bacilli with reaction of *B. coli* were isolated from the heart blood, but no abnormal bacteria were found on fæcal culture.

Post-mortem.—The alimentary canal down to the cæcum showed no change and the principal viscera also appeared normal. The cæcum and adjoining part of large intestine was deeply injected and inflamed and resembled acute dysentery. The mucous membrane was congested, thickened and velvety and showed well-marked ulceration in patches. There was an ulcer also in the sigmoid flexure. Small hæmorrhages were scattered through the large bowel.

Micro-histology.—The changes in the alimentary tract were similar but not so advanced as in Monkey 328. The small intestine showed decided degenerative changes with withering of the villi and superficial desquamation. The mesenteric glands showed well-marked toxic necrosis and the spleen contained a large amount of black pigment which did not give the iron reaction. The liver and spleen showed toxic changes in the parenchyma. The large bowel was extensively diseased as in the previous cases.

Control Monkey 331.

Deficiency diet commenced on 8th August 1927.

No infected feeds.

Clinical Course.—Its weight, about 3,000 grammes, was maintained till the end of October, when it commenced to fall rapidly till it reached 2,080 grammes at the time of death on 28th November 1927. Signs of scurvy were noted on 29th October 1927 and were noted irregularly till time of death. Diarrhœa noted on 26th November 1927. Dysenteric symptoms not noted. The animal became very ill a few days before death.

Bacteriological Examination.—No amœbæ found in fresh preparations. The plates showed the usual growth of cocci and coliform lactose fermenters, but there were also present a number of lactose non-fermenters which gave the reaction of *B. dysentericæ* Flexner and were agglutinated by both 'Flexner and Y' sera. This appeared to be a genuine 'Flexner and Y' dysentery.

Post-mortem.—The mucous membrane of the stomach was congested and showed ecchymosis in several places. The small intestine showed no change.

The cæcum was ulcerated and showed the changes found in dysentery. One ulcer in the head of the cæcum had perforated and an abscess had formed and had become adherent to the liver which was infiltrated at the area of contact. The lymph glands were enlarged and matted together around the abscess. Other small ulcers were present in the lower part of the larger bowel.

Micro-histology.—The changes here were limited to the large intestine, particularly the cæcum, the mucous membrane of which was in a state of homogeneous degeneration as if infiltrated with amyloid substance (which did not give the amyloid reaction). The normal structure and staining reaction of this part of the gut was lost. A condition of toxic necrosis was present at other levels in the large intestine and the parenchyma of the liver, kidney and mesenteric glands was similarly affected. There was increase of iron in the liver. There was an abscess extending into the liver substance at one place, but bacteria were not detected in this area.

Control Monkey 332.

Deficiency diet begun on 8th August 1927.

No infected feeds.

Clinical Course.—Maintained its weight at about 2,400 grammes till end of October, when it began to fall rapidly, reaching 1,790 grammes at death on 23rd November 1927. On 15th October 1927, began to show signs of incipient scurvy, ecchymosis and swelling of the eyelids. The gums were noted to be scorbutic on 5th November 1927. The animal was put on orange juice in the later stages but it did not improve. No diarrhœa or dysentery were noted during life.

Bacteriological Examination.—Not done.

Post-mortem.—Portions of the large intestine showed slight inflammatory signs with submucous hæmorrhages and thickening of mucosa. No ulcers were seen. The remaining organs were normal, but hæmorrhages were found in the muscles and other signs of scurvy.

Micro-histology.—The changes in the large bowel were of a slight nature and showed early degree of toxic degeneration without signs of inflammation. The principal changes were in the superficial mucosa.

PROTOCOL II.

Characters of different types of bacilli and cocci isolated from the contents of intestine of seven of the experimental monkeys.

Serial Numbers.	Morphology.	SUGAR FERMENTATION REACTIONS.											REMARKS.
		Gram.	Motility.	Lactose.	Glucose.	Maltose.	Saccharose.	Mannite.	Dulcite.	Litmus milk.	Indol.	Hæmolytic power.	
I. Lactose non-fermenters.													
1	B. (coliform) ..	—	—	—	A	..	—	A	—	—	+	..	Flexner type.
2	B. (") ..	—	—	—	AG	AG	AG	—	—	A	..	—	
3	B. (") ..	—	—	—	AG	AG	—	AG	—	—	..	..	
4	B. (fusiform sporing)	—	—	—	A	A	—	—	—	—	—	..	
5	B. (short) ..	—	+	—	A	—	..	—	—	—	..	—	
II. Lactose fermenters.													
6	B. (coliform) ..	—	—	A	A	A	A	A	A	A	..	..	
7	B. (short, thin) ..	—	—	A	AG	AG	AG	AG	—	AG	..	—	
8	B. (" ") ..	—	—	A	A	..	A	A	—	A	..	..	
9	B. (" ") ..	—	—	AG	AG	AG	—	AG	AG	AG	..	..	
10	B. (coliform) ..	—	—	AG	AG	AG	—	AG	AG	AG	..	—	
11	B. (") ..	—	—	AG	AG	AG	—	AG	AG	A	+	—	
12	B. (") ..	—	+	AG	AG	AG	AG	AG	—	A	..	..	
13	B. (medium thickness)	—	—	AG	AG	AG	—	AG	—	A	+	—	
14	B. (coliform) ..	—	—	AG	AG	AG	AG	AG	—	C	—	—	
15	B. (") ..	—	—	—	..	—	—	—	—	A	..	..	
III. Cocci.													
16	Co. (round) ..	+	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	
17	Co. (minute diplo) ..	+	—	—	A	—	—	—	—	—	..	—	
18	Co. (diplo) ..	+	—	—	A	—	A	—	—	C	..	—	
19	Co. (large) ..	+	—	—	A	A	A	A	A	—	..	—	
20	Co. (") ..	+	..	—	A	A	A	—	—	—	..	—	
21	Co. ..	+	—	A	A	A	A	—	—	A	..	..	
22	Co. (small, round) ..	+	..	A	A	A	A	A	—	A	..	—	
23	Co. (minute) ..	+	—	A	A	A	A	A	—	C	..	—	
24	Co. (diplo) ..	+	..	—	A	A	A	—	—	—	..	..	

Note.—Group I. Contains lactose non-fermenters.

Group II. Contains lactose fermenters mostly *B. coli* and its congeners.

Group III. Contains the various types of cocci present.

Fig. 1.

Fig. 2.

Fig. 3.

Fig. 4.

EXPLANATION OF PLATE XI.

- Fig. 1. Low power magnification of ileum of monkey showing coagulation necrosis of superficial mucosa, and of large areas in the submucous layer.
- „ 2. Cæcum of Monkey 331 showing partial destruction of mucous layer and fibrotic changes in submucous layer.
- „ 3. Cæcum of Monkey 281 showing earlier degenerative changes in mucous membrane.
- „ 4. Cæcum of Monkey 331 showing changes similar to those in Fig. 2.
- „ 5. Large intestine of Monkey 327 showing coagulative necrosis of mucous membrane.
- „ 6. Duodenum of Monkey 332 showing similar changes with early sloughing of mucous membrane and irritation and thickening of submucous layer.

EXPLANATION OF PLATE XII.

- Fig. 1.** Changes in duodenum of Monkey 332 similar to preceding.
- Figs. 2, 3 and 4.** Cæcum of Monkey 328 showing the structure of one of the nodules depicted in the coloured plate. Extensive coagulation necrosis of mucous membrane with fibrosis and small celled infiltration of submucous layers. All glandular and epithelial elements are destroyed and replaced by subacute inflammatory tissue.
- Fig. 5.** Low power section of liver showing toxic changes in lower cells and their destruction in certain areas.
- „ **6.** Same as Fig. 5 under higher magnification showing toxic changes in liver cells.

Fig. 1.

Fig. 2.

Fig. 3.

Fig. 4.

Fig. 1.

Fig. 2.

Fig. 3.

Fig. 4.

EXPLANATION OF PLATE XIII.

- Fig. 1. Shows extensive toxic necrosis of the renal tubules.
- „ 2. Shows changes in Lieberkühn's follicles of large intestine at the edge of a necrosed area.
- „ 3. Shows the invasion of the mucosa at the margin of a necrotic area by inflammatory cells. The glandular elements are almost completely destroyed.
- „ 4. Shows the invasion of the deeper layer of the submucosa in the affected part of the intestine by numerous bacteria.
- „ 5. The invasion of a villus by slender curved bacilli (magnification about 1,000).
- „ 6. Similar bacilli (magnification about 3,000) lying in the submucous layer of large intestine. These bacilli during life showed a slow serpiginous motility and could not be recovered by culture.

EXPLANATION OF PLATE XIV.

Shows the cecum of experimental Monkey 328. The mucous membrane is inflamed and there are a number of necrotic nodules capped with sloughs protruding from the surface.

PLATE XIV.
CÆCUM
OF
EXPERIMENTAL MONKEY NO. 328.

CHART I.
Showing weights of experimental monkeys.

